

Permeable pavement clogging laboratory experiments using rainfall simulators

Angélica Goya, Juan Naves, Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, Raquel Viturro and Alfredo Jácome

Universidade da Coruña, Water and Environmental Engineering Group (GEAMA), A Coruña, Spain
angelica.goya@udc.es, juan.naves@udc.es, jose.anta@udc.es, joaquin.suarez@udc.es, raquel.viturro@udc.es, alfredo.jacome@udc.es

Abstract

Sustainable urban Drainage Systems (SuDS) are becoming a common solution to address the increase in flow discharges, runoff volumes and pollutants concentrations caused by urban expansion. Among them, the use of permeable pavements is nowadays widespread due to their demonstrated effectiveness in managing and treating stormwater. However, there is great uncertainty in how the clogging of permeable pavements affects their long-term performance in terms of permeability reduction and pollution removal efficiency. Therefore, this study focused first in assessing the influence of clogging on the rainfall drained through porous asphalt slabs of 0.4 m x 0.4 m x 0.15 m. The hydrology behavior and removal efficiency of the asphalt were analyzed for different scenarios and grades of clogging by adding surface sediment loads between simulated rain events. In addition, a porous layer of the asphalt analyzed was used for the retrofitting of an impermeable concrete surface of a 36 m² full-scale street section physical model that uses the same system to simulate rain. The objective is to analyze the impact of the porous asphalt layer on the hydrology and the mobilization of pollutants under full-scale and laboratory-controlled conditions, and to compare with previous tests developed using a conventional impervious concrete pavement.

Keywords: Urban drainage; SuDS; Permeable pavement; Clogging; Rainfall simulator

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable urban Drainage Systems (SuDS) are becoming a common solution to address the increase in flow discharges and runoff volumes caused by urban growth. Among them, the use of permeable pavements is nowadays widespread due to their demonstrated effectiveness in managing and treating stormwater. However, there is great uncertainty in how the clogging of permeable pavements affects their long-term performance in terms of permeability reduction and pollution removal efficiency.

The installation of permeable pavements in an urban environment involves the reception of dust and dirt coming from different sources as atmospheric deposition, organic materials, runoff, and degradation of the filter media materials themselves, in addition to other inputs. This dust and dirt, consisting of materials of different sizes, are partially retained in the porous space. In fact, the retention of these elements is a favorable process in terms of improving the quality of runoff water, because these particles are commonly associated with different pollutants, some of them listed as very dangerous such as heavy metals contained in road dust (Goya et al., 2020; Sansalone et al., 2012). However, retention also implies clogging of the permeable pavement, caused a hydraulic constrain by limiting infiltration reducing its proven effectiveness in stormwater management and treatment (Davies et al., 2002).

In this study, the impact of permeable pavements on the hydrology and the mobilization of pollutants is assessed by comparing the obtained results against conventional impervious pavements. Using the physical models available at the Center for Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering (CITEEC) of the University of A Coruña, the hydrology behavior and removal efficiency of PA-16 asphalt slabs of 0.4 m x 0.4 m x 0.15 m were analyzed for different clogging scenarios by adding surface sediment loads between simulated rain events using the small-scale rainfall simulator. Then, a porous layer of the same asphalt was used for the retrofitting of an impermeable concrete surface of a 36 m² full-scale street section physical model that uses the same system to simulate rain (Naves et al., 2020).

The overall objective is to analyze the impact of the porous asphalt layer on the hydrology and the mobilization of pollutants under laboratory-controlled conditions, comparing this with previous tests developed using a conventional impervious concrete pavement (Naves et al., 2021).

2. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the experimental setup and procedure followed to assess the long-term clogging using porous asphalt slabs in a small rainfall simulator is described first. Then, the retrofitting of the street section

full-scale physical model using a layer of the same porous asphalt, and preliminary experiments are presented.

2.1 Small rainfall simulator experimental setup

An experimental bench has been developed to allow the simulation of 1 m^2 rainfall shown in Figure 1a, to analyze the long-term clogging of permeable slabs. Some modifications can be made according to the characteristics and dimensions of the elements to be tested. The simulator consists of a drippers-based system that can generate three types of realistic and uniform rainfall of 30, 50, and 80 mm/h intensity, as described in Naves et al. (2020).

The permeable elements of Spanish type PA-16 porous asphalt consist of asphalt slabs with 22.6% void-ratio, 4.03% of bitumen, and dimensions of $0.4 \text{ m} \times 0.4 \text{ m} \times 0.15 \text{ m}$. The slabs were partially sealed on the perimeter to allow the flow of the water towards the filter tank, and then installed under the dripper system, on an equivalent impermeable surface arranged with a slope of 2% as shown in Figure 1b and c. Stormwater flow discharges and volumes are recorded in two cylindrical collection tanks. One tank collects the water that infiltrates through the slab, and the second one collects the water that drains as the slab becomes clogged with the distributed sediment.

Figure 1. a) Rainfall simulator, b) porous asphalt slab and c) installed slab during clogging tests.

Initially, the hydrological characterization of the impervious surface was carried out by evaluating the runoff flow generated by a uniform rainfall of 80 mm/h, and for different time periods (5, 10, 15, and 30 minutes). Once this preliminary test was carried out, a hydrological characterization of the PA-16 slab was performed under the same conditions of rainfall duration and intensity. This allowed comparing the results of the outflow hydrographs of the two surfaces. In addition, to measure the initial permeability of the slab, LCS permeameter was used, following the Spanish standard NLT-327/00 (CEDEX, 2000).

Stormwater filtered through the system is collected in the cylindrical reservoir circular collection tank through a funnel for online measuring of water discharge and turbidity samples. In the same way, as sediment clogs the pavement, runoff might be generated and conducted to the second collection tank. The variations of permeability for different grades of clogging were measured at three control points placed in the center of the slab.

Using the above information as a reference scenario, clogging of asphalt slabs was evaluated by assessing the variation in the permeability, and the infiltration and runoff hydrographs. Road deposited sediments were collected in the parking lots of University of A Coruña campus. Sediments were calcined and prepared to be classified into three different particle size distributions: fine (T1), coarse (T2), and realistic (T3). T1 ($63\text{--}125 \mu\text{m}$) and T2 ($250\text{--}500 \mu\text{m}$) have a uniform particle size distribution with a mean diameter d_{50} of

104 μm and 391 μm , and a dry density ρ_s of 2931 kg/m³ and 2652 kg/m³, respectively. On the other hand, T3 particle size distribution ranges between 0.5 and 1000 μm (d_{50} =282 μm , ρ_s =2929 kg/m³) and represents a realistic graded road deposit sediments.

Prior to the simulation of the 30 minutes 80 mm/h rainfall, the sediments were uniformly distributed over the slab. To assess slab clogging, different sediments loads were gradually deposited and after each buildup test, filtered and runoff stormwater flow discharges were recorded. Tests were performed with incremental loads starting at 0.1 kg/m² for the first cumulative surface load, and then by adding 0.5 kg/m² until the clogging effect became evident. Pavement permeability was measured with LCS permeameter after each kg/m² accumulated. Once the clogging of the PA-16 slab was evident and the surface was vacuumed, a rain was simulated again, the permeability was measured, and so the recovery capacity of the slab was determined. Finally, the mass balance was measured by calculating the vacuumed sediment out of the surface of the slab and the mass of sediment dragged into the filtration and run-off tanks.

2.2 Full-scale street section physical model

This experimental setup consists of a full-scale street section physical model of 36 m² with an impervious concrete asphalt surface retrofitted with the same porous asphalt used in the previous tests (Figure 2a). Surface topography was measured using a point gauge in a rectangular grid of 50 x 50 cm using the procedure defined in Naves et al. (2019). The error bounds of the measured horizontal coordinates were assumed to be approximately 1 cm for the horizontal coordinates, and about 1mm for the vertical coordinates. The rainfall-runoff generated is drained through two gully pots and a downstream lateral channel where flow discharges and sediment concentrations are measured by using v-notches in lower deposits and by grabbing manual samples he impervious concrete road surface of the facility, which were previously used to perform high definition hydraulic, wash-off and sediment transport experiments (Naves et al., 2021) has been retrofitted using a permeable asphalt layer to comparatively assess the influence of this type of SuDS in the quantity and quality of stormwater flowing into the model gully pots.

Three experimental cases with 30, 50 and 80 mm/h were simulated during 300 s, this representing a range from medium to high intensity rain events. Pavement permeability was measured using the LCS permeameter in a 50 x 50 cm regular grid (Figure 2b).

Figure 2. a) Porous asphalt layer placed over a street section physical model of 36 m² and b) variable head permeameter used during the experiments.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.3 Analysis of porous pavement slabs

Figure 3 shows the difference between the hydrographs drained by the PA16 slab and an equivalent impermeable surface for a constant rainfall of 80 mm/h and different durations of 5, 10, 15, and 30 minutes. It

can be observed that the porous slab produces a delay in the actual peak flow, and a small reduction in the maximum flow for the different rainfall intensities. The small differences between impervious and permeable pavements hydrographs recorded in the small-scale rainfall simulator are due to the outflow boundary conditions of the slab. As can be seen in the next section, in the large scale test the differences are more noticeable. After the maximum rainfall duration of 30 minutes, the retention capacity was 0.13 L.

Figure 3. Hydrographs comparison between the flow drained through the PA-16 slab, and the impervious surface for the four rainfall durations (5, 10, 15 and 30 minutes).

Regarding clogging tests, Figure 4a shows the effect of accumulated sediment load and granulometry in pavement permeability measured with LCS test. The average initial permeability of the slabs used for the three particle size distributions was 21787 mm/h. The obtained results highlight the importance of sediment characterization in pavement clogging. Thus, while the reduction in the slab permeability for an initial load of 1 kg/m² of fine sediment was almost imperceptible (less than 2% of the change in the initial permeability), coarser and realistic grain sizes with this same initial load clogged the slabs to a greater degree, resulting in permeability reductions of 20% and 60%, respectively.

Figure 4. a) Mean permeability measures on the center of the PA-16 slab for different grain sizes and sediment loads, b) Maximum filtered and runoff drained discharges registered for the realistic granulometry and different grades of clogging

Based on this initial evaluation, it was decided to continue the test with the realistic granulometry until reach a “critical” cumulative clogging load which allows runoff overland flow. Figure 4 a. shows that the reduction in permeability for the 2 kg/m² cumulative load test is around 85% and with a load of 4 kg/m² the slab is clogged according to the results of LCS variable head permeameter. Figure 4b shows the influence of the surface load on the average filtered and runoff flow discharge. It can be observed that from a cumulative load of 1.5 kg/m², rainwater began to drain with greater difficulty through the slab and start to generate runoff.

The runoff generated by the clogging caused for the first 2 kg/m² of sediment was roughly 0.002 L/s. Runoff discharge till 0.004 L/s after 5 Kg/m² were added to the surface. Conversely, filtered runoff discharge is reduced to 0.002 L/s. The critical value of the cumulative sediment load obtained was between 4.5 and 5 kg/m².

Lastly, Figure 5 presents the distribution of the sediment loads after the mass balance assessment performed after the tests with the different granulometries. Surface sediment loads was measured by vacuuming process of the surface. The sediments in the filtered and runoff were recorded at the collection tanks. Sediment loads in the porous asphalt was estimated by difference. It can be observed that sediment loads in flow discharges are below the 4% of the total deposited load, highlighting the pollution reduction efficiency of the pavement. Trapped sediment in the slabs ranges between 75% to 98%, as a function of the particle size distribution. In the case of the test with the realistic granulometry, the slab retention of the total sediment load was 83%. After surface vacuuming, the slab recovers a small fraction of the initial infiltration capacity (about 8% of the permeability).

Figure 5. Mass balances obtained at the end of the three tests, representing the percentage of sediments deposited in the pavement surface, inside the slabs and mobilized by filtration and overland flows.

3.4 Analysis of the porous asphalt at full-scale model

Preliminary results gathered in the full-scale rainfall simulator model are presented in this section. Figure 6 shown the thickness of the permeable porous asphalt. The average width of the overlying layer is 4.95 cm with an averaged permeability of 22822 mm/h.

Figure 6. Thickness of the permeable pavement used in the large-scale rainfall simulator.

Figure 7 shows the flow discharge into gully pot 2 of the physical model for a 5 minute rainfall intensity of 30, 50 and 80 mm/h with the previous impermeable pavement and the retrofitted porous asphalt. The obtained results showed that the permeable pavement layer disposed over the street concrete surface reduces by 50% the peak of the drained flow in the worst case studied (rain intensity of 80 mm/h during 300 s). In addition, the hydrographs measured with the permeable pavement presented a lag in the runoff peak of more than 3 minutes in case of the highest rain intensity tested. These results confirmed and quantified the benefits of this permeable pavements in urban stormwater management and the importance of model scale and setup in analyzing this SuDS typology.

Figure 7. Comparison between the flow drained through the gully pots from the street section with and without the permeable pavement for the three rain intensities that the rainfall simulator can generate (30, 50 and 80 mm/h).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a porous asphalt was hydrologically characterized by comparing drained discharges with an equivalent impervious surface in a small and a large-scale physical model using different rain intensities and durations. Then, the permeability of the porous pavement was investigated as the pavement becomes clogged with different road deposit sediments with different particle size distributions.

Significant differences were found in the permeable pavement outflow discharge measured in the porous slabs and the full-scale model. In the full-scale model, the porous asphalt provoked a peak discharge reduction and delay which is not prominent in the small-scale configuration due to the imposed boundary conditions. Then, the permeability of the porous pavement was investigated as the pavement becomes clogged. First, it has been observed a high influence of sediment granulometry in clogging process, being key the use of continuous grain size distributions to reach reliable results. Then, asphalt slabs have been clogged from a cumulative sediment load of 4 - 5 kg/m², generating surface runoff on the pavement surface. Efforts should be done in increasing understanding of clogging processes at different scales in order to better transfer laboratory results to real world deployments.

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6. REFERENCES

- Davies, W., Pratt, J., and Scott, A. (2002). Laboratory Study of Permeable Pavement Systems to Support Hydraulic Modeling. *9 Conference on Urban Drainage ICUD, Global Solutions for Urban Drainage*, 1–9
- Goya, A., Zafra, C., and Rodríguez, J. (2020). Methodological trends in the assessment of the pollution and risks degree of heavy metals present in urban road sediments. *Revista UIS Ingenierías*, 19(4), 133–148.
- Naves, J., García, J. T., Puertas, J., and Anta, J. (2021). Assessing different imaging velocimetry techniques to measure shallow runoff velocities during rain events using an urban drainage physical model. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 25(2), 885–900. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-885-2021>
- Naves, J., Anta, J., Suárez, J., and Puertas, J. (2020a). Development and Calibration of a New Drinker-Based Rainfall Simulator for Large-Scale Sediment Wash-Off Studies. *Water*, 12, 152.
- Naves, J., Anta, J., Suárez, J. and Puertas, J. (2020b). Hydraulic, wash-off and sediment transport experiments in a full-scale urban drainage physical model. *Scientific Data*, 7, 44.

- Naves, J., Anta, J., Suárez, J. and Puertas, J. (2019). Using a 2D shallow water model to assess Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) and Structure from Motion (SfM) techniques in a street-scale urban drainage physical model. *Journal of Hydrology*, 575, 54-65.
- Sansalone, J., Kuang, X., Ying, G., and Ranieri, V. (2012). Filtration and clogging of permeable pavement loaded by urban drainage. *Water Research*, 46(20), 6763–6774.